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CRISTAL

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

[D 1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements]

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
Aipo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
BMVI	Bundesministerium für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur
DSS	Decision Support System
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IV	Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l
IWT	Inland waterway transport
KPI	Key performance indicator
LNG	Liquid Natural Gas
NRW	Northrhine-Westfalia
NST	Standard goods classification for transport statistics
SHM	Structural health monitoring
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VNF	Voies navigables de France

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1. Executive Summary

The main goal of this first deliverable of the project is to provide the rationale for the CRISTAL project. The deliverable outlines the background and the overall framework of inland waterway transport in Europe and puts the three pilot sites into relation to the dominating inland waterway regions in Europe. Together with the description of responsibilities of the involved infrastructure authorities, the outline of the planned research indicates that while the French pilot site already constitutes of a well-managed and relatively well demanded transport infrastructure, both the Italian and the Polish sites must be considered to be rather in a development phase for inland waterway.

Technologies developed and applied must take these heterogeneous conditions in the three pilot sites into account. In order that the infrastructure authorities benefit from the technologies and governance processes developed in the project, the dimensions and the scaling must be adapted. To this end this deliverable provides a necessary contribution, having compiled the responsibilities, the state of the art and the expectations and first requirements of the infrastructure authorities regarding the technology developments and adoptions in CRISTAL.

This deliverable will define the main aspects of the strategic vision, as requirements, solutions, current and future operations, and economic risks of stakeholders.¹ Deliverable 1.1 aims to describe and define the pilots by the own words of the pilot owners. Work steps include reviews of related projects and literature, stakeholder analysis (expert interviews). This deliverable will also detail the project's evaluation methodology.

1.1. Introduction

The CRISTAL project's ambition is to increase the availability and thus the attractiveness of the inland waterway transport mode. To this end, pilot sites are being set up in three regions of Europe, where the new to be developed technologies and processes will be tested and deployed. All three regions have in common that they are not among the most developed regions for inland waterways. While inland navigation takes place on the Seine and on the Moselle in France, this mode of transport is less developed on the almost unregulated rivers Po in Italy and Vistula in Poland.

The rationale for this project is the ambition to shift the modal split in the regions under consideration by at least 20% in favour of inland navigation. This can be achieved by the chosen technologies and measures i.e. a better data acquisition for the infrastructure operators but also for the users of the transport infrastructure, a better plannability regarding extreme weather events and other disturbances as well as a better monitoring of the status of the existing quay facilities and bank reinforcements.

In the CRISTAL project, technologies are developed to facilitate the management of an inland waterway and to better deal with the challenges of infrastructure maintenance, in particular:

- Sensors and fiber optic sensors for real time and continuous monitoring of critical section lines

¹ Remark: In the DoW the descriptions of Del 1.1. and 1.3 have been switched accidentally

- Intelligent Buoy system for real time and continuous monitoring of water-levels + counting passing ships + environmental parameters
- Structural health monitoring (SHM) of engineered infrastructures inspection radar technology
- Data Acquisition systems – if none is available
- Mobile Apps and dashboards for easily visualizing and querying KPIs (Key performance indicator) calculated from sensor data (from new sensors and already available sensors)
- Digital twins that will host and calculate the collected data
- A synchro-modal corridor management system for the users and potential users

The synchro-modal corridor management system will be created so that shippers, forwarders and barge operators can plan alternative means of transportation ahead in the case that closures or restrictions to the usability of the inland waterway are unavoidable despite all precautionary measures. The to be developed buoys and sensors measuring water levels and flow characteristics will contribute their data to the planned digital twins of the specific waterway segment.

Inland waterway infrastructure has always been vulnerable to extreme weather events, depending on the geography and geographical location. Many inland waterways do not have sufficient water all year round or suffer in their usability from high water situations caused by too much precipitation or snow melt. As a result, inland waterway transport is often discredited for causing increased costs and efforts during these downtimes, forcing transport companies to use other modes of transport as a substitute. So, inland navigation can benefit from a corridor synchro-modal management system if it ensures that participants in the transport market can continue their transport services via other transport modes during these unavoidable downtimes without much friction. The inland navigation industry benefits in the CRISTAL project through the development of state-of-the-art buoys and sensors, which as data providers support the infrastructure operators both in the daily operation with real-time data and in the planning of maintenance situations through the digital twin. Another support for infrastructure operators holds the application of testing the integrity and condition of concrete or masonry water facilities.

To conclude, CRISTAL aims at:

- Enhanced inland waterway infrastructure resilience to minimize downtimes of availability in IWT
- Synchro-modal solutions to bridge the unavoidable downtimes

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D1.1 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements	<p><i>This deliverable will define the main aspects of the strategic vision, as requirements, solutions, current and future operations and economic risks of stakeholders.</i></p> <p><i>Remark: In the DoW the descriptions of Del 1.1. and 1.3 have been switched accidentally</i></p>	<i>See hereunder Requirements part</i>	<i>Del 1.1 aims include to describe and define the pilots by the own words of the pilot owner</i>
TASKS			
Task 1.1 Domain Map and Vision Statement	<i>Task 1.1 Domain Map and Vision</i>	<p><i>Review of related projects and literature in Chapter 2</i></p> <p><i>Vision of the three pilots in Chapter 3</i></p> <p><i>Evaluation methodology in chapter 4</i></p> <p><i>Questionnaire in Annex 1</i></p>	<i>Work steps include reviews of related projects and literature, stakeholder risk analysis (scenario analysis & expert interviews). This task will detail the project's evaluation methodology. The latter will comprise a number of evaluation instruments and tools.</i>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The deliverable first provides a quick glance at the current situation with waterway transport in Europe. then traffic statistics. In the chapter Vision Statement, an overall description of three pilot sites is presented. The deliverable also contains a first methodological approach towards the evaluation

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

methodology. Generally, Deliverable D 1.1 should be regarded as a living document, summarizing and listing first findings and approached towards the project, that however can be revised at a later stage if necessary. Unfortunately, the questionnaire has not been completed by the Polish infrastructure authority yet, who are however not a project partner.

2. Domain Map

Within this chapter, a brief overview is provided about the IWT framework, in which the pilots operate.

2.1. IWT development and status until 2022

Together with road and rail transport, inland waterway transport is one of the three most important modes of land transport. Ships transport goods via inland waterways such as canals, rivers and lakes between inland ports and berths. Half of Europe's population lives in coastal regions or near inland waterways, and most European industrial centers are connected to the inland waterway network. Transporting goods by inland waterways can be beneficial, as convoys of push barges can carry more goods per unit distance (TKM) than any other land transport mode and could help reduce road traffic. The loading capacity of inland waterway vessels is equivalent to that of hundreds of trucks, which could help save transportation costs, reduce pollutant emissions, and mitigate road traffic congestion. (European Court of Auditors (2015))

Figure 1 - Transport performance of IWT in the EU-27 (Eurostat [IWW_GO_ATYGO] 2022)

In 2021, the transport performance on European inland waterways was around 135 million tonne-kilometers. Looking at the period 2018-2021, a fluctuation of the transport performance between 130 and 140 million tonne-kilometers is obvious in Figure 1.

IWT is mainly dependent on the water levels of the European inland waterways. This can be seen above all in the comparison between the years 2017 and 2018. Transport performance of IWT vessels fell by 11 percent in 2018, as water levels were historically low that year. With the starting Corona measures in 2020, inland waterway transport performance in the EU-27 fell again by 6 percent, compared to 2019. In 2021, the transport performance increased again by 3 percent, compared to 2020.

Figure 2 - Transport performance (Million TKM) of IWT by country (Eurostat [IWW_GO_ATYGO] 2022)

Inland waterway transport is a recognisable transport mode only in the member states Germany, the Netherlands, Romania, Belgium, and France, see Figure 2. Furthermore, as shown in figure 3 the inland waterway performance of all Rhine countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and Switzerland) accounted for 81.1% of the total inland waterway performance of the EU-27, including Switzerland. The second strongest region was the Danube region with 18.6% (excluding Ukraine). (CCNR. 2021)

Figure 3 - Contribution of IWW EU transport volumes per country (Eurostat [IWW_GO_ATYGO] 2022)

Focusing on IWT it is noticeable that most vessels on inland waterways in the EU-27 have been built before the year 2000. Not a lot of vessels were built after the 2000, resulting in an old and sometimes inefficient fleet. The European IWT fleet keeps being dominated by vessels older than 1974.

Figure 4 - Number of IWT vessels based on year of construction (Eurostat [IWW_EQ_AGE] 2022)

IWT has always been a transport mode for bulk transport and goods with the high weight density. On few transport corridors and reasoned by the accessibility off major seaports inland waterway transport has managed also to become the transport mode for unitised cargo like the container transports on the river Rhine. Goods that are mainly transported by inland waterway vessels belong to the group of containerized goods or bulk goods. Since load units are usually stacked on barges, we do not find much semi-trailers or swap-bodies as intermodal transport units on barges. In detail, the transport performance of bulk goods within the EU on IWT dominates. In 2021, the performance of transport of bulk goods was more than 10 times higher than containerized goods. This is reasoned by the weight density of the transported bulk goods.

Figure 5 - Transport by type of good in Million tkm (Eurostat [IWW_GO_ATYGO] 2022)

If IWT is compared to truck and rail transportation, it is obvious that the modal split has changed only little over the past years. Road transport remains the mostly used mode of transport with 77.4% in 2020. Compared to 2017, there has even been an increase of 2 percent through volumes which have been shifted from rail to truck. Rail transport is the second most used mode of transport, accounting for 16.8% of goods transported in 2020. The least used mode of transport is still inland waterway transportation, which transported 5.8% of the goods in 2020.

Figure 6 - Modal split EU-27 (Eurostat [TRAN_HV_FRMOD] 2022)

Trend analysis Inland Waterway Transportation

The inland waterway transport sector, like most other transport sectors, is faced with the task of processing a likely larger transport demand in the future. In contrast to the largest transport sector, road, the transport sector of IWT still has free capacity on its infrastructure, which could be used, for example, by a sustainable and multimodal transport solution. Overall, numerous indicators can be found in IWT that give an idea of the current and future trends and thus the future use of the canal network by IWT (Fraunhofer 2020).

Often the river Rhine (and the river Scheldt) is taken as the example for European inland waterway transport while it must be regarded rather as an exemption than the rule. No other river or canal system links major deep seaports with a highly populated area and massive industrial complex at its banks. Even the comparison to the other large European river, the Danube, falls short. The Danube does not link any major seaport like Rotterdam nor does it connect a comparable density of industrial areas and populated areas like the Ruhr area. The transport demand is just not the same. Both rivers enjoy a good navigation status because they originate in the Alps. This is also true for the river Po, which has also high-water supply from the Alps. Other major rivers originate in hilly or mountainous areas where precipitation is less, and snow falls occur rarely. This creates simply for morphologic regions other dimensions of the river and other water levels. Examples for such rivers are for instance the rivers Vistula, Odra, Seine and the Moselle.

The European canal system consists of a network of artificial waterways in which the water levels are regulated through locks. The dense canal system exists in Germany, where at two places even crossings of this canals do exist in Minden and in Magdeburg. Also in Germany, the Rhein-Main-Donau canal links

the two river and canal systems of the Danube and the Rhine by overcoming the watershed between the two geographies. Also in the Netherlands and in Belgium industrial areas are linked via a dense system of canals. The most recent ambitious project of new canal IWT infrastructure in Europe is the French Canal Seine-Nord Europe (CSNE) that will link the Seine to the North Range Ports and regions of Belgium and the Netherlands.

The statistical introduction to IWT is now followed by a consideration of possible future developments based on factors and trends such as, future policy objectives, projects already implemented or still underway and statistical figures to identify trends. Likewise, global megatrends were included in the IWT trend analysis. These megatrends were collected in the following figure.

2.2.Future perspectives for IWT

IWT is affected just like any other transport modes by the dominant megatrends. The question is, how IWT can use and apply these megatrends to regain market shares or at least to compensate for the loss of bulk commodities transported.

Figure 7: Megatrends, own illustration (Zukunftsinstitut GmbH 2020)

A total of 78 completed or ongoing projects related to IWT have been collected and assigned to the trends shown in Figure 7. In this way, the megatrends presented could be weighted according to their relevance for IWT. Through the categorization of the projects, the trends towards sustainability and digitalization can be noted as trendsetting for IWT. Here, topics such as autonomous driving, alternative fuels and propulsion as well as improved networking of stakeholders are particularly present.

Due to the increasing relevance of sustainability in all areas of society, sustainability also comes into focus in IWT. However, general trends regarding the modal split in the transport sector already supports the future development of IWT. Its potential in free capacity. This would enable inland waterway transport to take over a larger share of total freight transport and partially offset the growth in freight transport forecast for the future.

Several projects can be identified that will improve IWT's attractiveness in terms of sustainability. Developments in the field of liquefied natural gas (LNG) show great potential for inland shipping as a fuel and a possible commodity to ship. The BinGas project at the University of Duisburg Essen showed that the greatest advantage of LNG as a fuel for shipping is a significantly reduces emissions of CO₂ and particulate matter compared to the more common diesel engine. Besides that various studies have already shown the functionality of an LNG-based system in extended operation. (Now GmbH 2019) However, the establishment of LNG as a fuel still requires an increased development of the LNG tank infrastructure along the various water corridors.(BMVI 2014) But in this way, a shift to LNG-fueled inland vessels could further strengthen the transport sector as the trend toward sustainability continues.

Another trend that has been identified and is advancing in logistics is digitalization, which is presenting IWT with both new challenges and new opportunities. With 37 projects, most of the projects considered can be assigned to this area, with particular emphasis on the development of assistance systems, autonomous driving, simulations and the use of Big Data.(El Moctar 2014) For example, initial trials and studies are underway in the A-SWARM project to develop autonomously operated water vehicles on inland waterways, with the aim of making IWT more cost-efficient.(Schiffbau-Versuchsanstalt Potsdam GmbH 2019) As in the LAESSI project, research is also being carried out on assistance systems to support the captain, which is the precursor to autonomous driving in IWT.(DLR 2018) Optimizing networking and communication between all players along the supply chain through various approaches is another goal of many transport and logistic projects. One example is the secure and uniform networking of the players to further strengthen the resilience of the supply chains and of IWT.

However, there are also developments within the transport sector outside of the megatrends that will have an influence on the future of IWT. There are the changes in the amounts of total freight volumes and trends in the other modes of transport as already described, as well as the general developments in the freight structure towards smaller units, caused by the decreasing relevance of bulk goods such as coal and ore.(Statistisches Landesamt NRW 2019) However, since it is precisely these bulk goods that currently account for a large proportion of the volumes transported on inland waterways, a decline in ton-kilometres within inland waterway transport is to be expected. The declining numbers of bulk cargoes could be counteracted, for example, by encouraging and making container transport in IWT more cost-efficient. For such a contemplation there is however no evidence. While it is possible to identify any untapped potential, the realisation of working transport solution has often been restricted to factory-to-factory transports or special commodities (e.g. large gas-turbines).

2.3. Traffic statistics of the three pilot sites

As stated above, traffic volumes in all three sites are modestly low. The exception is the Seine, however, also the Seine is not comparable with the river Rhine or the Danube in terms of volumes transported and transport work undertaken. The commodities transported illustrate again the dilemma; much transport in IWT are bulk goods, of which some will diminish soon, like coal or coke. Unitised cargo, mostly reported in NST 2007 group 20 as Other Cargo (since it's nature is not recognisable), doesn't play a considerable role yet. That however would be a large potential transport market segment, inland waterway could attract, if quality performance and transport costs were competitive.

Traffic volumes on the French pilot sites have been for the past twenty years relatively stable in the Seine Bassin at around 20 million Tonnes per year, however, volumes in the Bassin Nord Est however have lost

almost the half from 10 million tonnes (2000) to 5,8 million tonnes 2012, reasoned by a drop in mineral fuels. The Seine Bassin is dominated by Crude materials incl. building materials, much reasoned by the large port of Rouen being a multi-modal port which specialises in bulk and agri-bulk commodities. The Bassin Nord-Est shows a considerable amount of agricultural products.

Figure 8: Traffic volumes on the French pilot sites 2021 (VNF Transport statistics 2022)

The Italian pilot site at the river Po reports the following figures for 2020. It shows the smallest traffic volumes of all three countries covered. What is remarkable is the large amount in the NST group 16, which is transport equipment, not necessarily utilised cargo within containers but e.g. the containers or trailers themselves as produced goods.

Figure 9: Traffic volumes on the Italian pilot site 2020 (Ministero delle infrastrutture e dei trasporti 2022)

The Polish IWT statistics are for the whole country Poland, not only for some segments of the rivers concerned. They however include the pilot site and show the following traffic volumes. The dominant group 3 consists of building materials like sand, stones or gravel, here counted as mining materials. Also in Poland, no unitised cargo is visible in NST group 20.

Figure 10: Traffic volumes in Poland, including the Polish pilot site 2021 (University of Gdansk 2022)

2.4. Issue of changing climate conditions for inland waterway infrastructure

Recently, even the busiest inland waterways have seen their usability severely limited by effects attributed to climate change. After 2018 the second severe Europe-wide drought in the spring and summer 2022 severely limited navigation on the Rhine, but also on other rivers. Some rivers are experiencing an almost constant limited usability also because they have not been deepened any longer after past flood events. The avoidance of future floodings became priority through renaturation over navigability. One example of this is the Elbe River between the Czech Republic, Saxony and Hamburg in Germany after the Elbe flooding in 2002.

Some of the infrastructure operators stressed in the questionnaire that climate change is already a major threat to their operation or that it severely increases their infrastructure maintenance efforts. However, the expectation is shared that climate change will lead to less favourable conditions for IWT. In recent scientific literature this issue is tackled and most available papers come to the conclusion that even if the latest droughts of 2018 and 2022 are not sufficient to constitute a major trend for low water in the future.

However, climate change seems responsible for the widespread occurrence of low water levels during summertime causing a restriction of transport capacity. The number of occurrences is expected to rise (Jonkeren et al., 2013). (Müller 2013) however states that a broader and continuous data base is necessary for a better flood risk management.

The Kliwas project (BMVI 2015) has looked into the issue with the water levels of The Rhine, Elbe, and Danube to determine the impact of climate change on waterways and shipping. Discussing the Rhine, in the near future (2021-2050) there might either be no change in frequency of low-water levels or even a decrease in frequency. High water levels will most likely increase. In the far future (2071-2100), water levels will behave similarly to the near future but with an increased number of high-water levels. It is estimated that transport cost for inland waterway transport will increase by up to 10%. In both timeframes, low-water level events will be more impactful on transport than high water levels because of their duration – even if they are forecast to be less in number. For the Elbe or Danube, no observable change is predicted in the near future. In the far future, frequency of low-water levels will increase. Precipitation is expected to decrease in the summer and not change in winter.

The Rhine Commission cannot confirm that low water levels are occurring more often than in the first half of the 21st century. What they confirm is that the impact of low water levels on the dependent industries have drastically risen. One example of the world's largest chemical company BASF shows, how industries depending on barge transport may react. BASF decided that three new types of ships will be constructed, all somewhat specialized for low water levels. A low-water tanker, a gas tanker and low water specialized ship of unknown type. The gas tanker can transport 650 tons at a water level of 30 centimetres. In addition to new ships, BASF implemented a digital early warning system for low water, which can warn the company up to six weeks before to allow for adjustments in logistics. The loading points are being upgraded, to allow for alternative transport methods such as rail, if ships are not viable. However, this situation with the European inland waterway transport sector is far from being explained or reasoned by climate change only. Transport work of inland waterway transport in the EU has not grown in the last ten years.

3. Vision statement; the pilot sites in France, Italy and Poland

All the pilot sites have in common that they do not belong to the most intensely used inland waterway corridors in Europe. To illustrate the current situation, the three pilot sites are described and traffic and transport statistics are presented.

3.1. Stakeholders in the pilots

The CRISTAL consortium consists of many stakeholders, however, not for all pilots the infrastructure authority is partner in the project.

Stakeholder	Actor's role	Pilot site	Project partner
Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po Aipo	Infrastructure authority	Italy	YES
Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l	Infrastructure authority	Italy	YES
Uniontrasporti s.cons.r.l	Competence center	Italy	YES
University of Gdansk	Competence center	Poland	YES
Wody Polskie	Infrastructure authority	Poland	NO
Voies navigables de France VNF	Infrastructure authority	France	YES

Table 2: Stakeholders in the pilot sites

3.2. The French pilot site at the rivers Moselle and Seine

The Seine is a fluvial axis that connects the French national port complex (HAROPA with the ports of Le Havre, Rouen and Paris) to the Ile-de-France region, which is the largest French conurbation. River traffic today contributes significantly to the transport of goods within this major economic area, whether it be construction materials, agricultural products, energy products, various containerized goods, transport of waste, vehicles or heavy packages.

However, its use could be greatly strengthened. In fact, as an unsaturated transport infrastructure, the Seine would be able to have 4 times more traffic than it has today. It can be considered a credible and ecologically alternative to road freight transport and constitutes a major asset for reinforcing the positions of the ports of the Seine axis and development of their hinterland.

With a length of 233km between Rouen and Paris, the Seine is a large-gauge class Vb river (European classification of waterways), open to 24-hour navigation. It allows 185 meters long barges which carry up to 5,000 tonnes of goods, the equivalent of 250 trucks. On average, between 10,000 and 16,000 ships go annually through the locks of the Seine, 85% of which are freight ships.

Traffic is enabled thanks to a high level of service (physical and digital service) but it needs to be improved to meet the multifunctionality of the waterway. Maintaining the downstream Seine axis under minimum performance conditions should make it possible to continue to perform the two main functions of the river,

- navigation and
- hydraulic management.

Maintaining these two functions requires a good structural and operating condition of the infrastructure, but also real-time monitoring, short-term operational forecasting and coordinated and optimized management of traffic, structures and water levels.

Figure 11: The Seine; snap shots of infrastructure and locks (VNF 2022)

Figure 12: Northern France inland waterway network (VNF 2022)

The large gauge Moselle (class V) running over 152 km allows the passage of self-propelled and pushed convoys of more than 3,000 tons to the North Sea ports via the Rhine. Other waterways of Freycinet gauge being accessible for commercial navigation converge towards the Moselle. These may have a role as feeder lanes. The Moselle directly serves two major cities (Metz and Nancy), the industrial basins of Thionville and Pont-à-Mousson and the Saar basin and has public and private ports, including the port of Metz (9th biggest in France with 2.183.000 tonnes in 2019).

Floods can impact navigation with hazards such as ice jams or landings, as well as movement of markings. These hazards also generate disturbances. The number of disturbances impacting navigation remains relatively constant between 3 to 4 per year. The possible flood period seems to extend.

Measures are taken during the low water period over a period from beginning of July to end of October (or even December). VNF has always faced difficulties in regulating flows on the Moselle. Indeed, for low to medium flows, flow waves are observed which propagate upstream to downstream of the Moselle.

The regulation for both dams and hydroelectric plants consists of maintaining as closely as possible the regulation level set upstream of each dam. This mode of regulation does not make it possible to reduce the flow waves but in some cases accentuates them. Regulation taking into account an improvement in flow regulation will lead to a greater tidal range around the regulation level upstream of the dams.

For each reach, in addition to the already formalized ‘target’ regulation range, a maximum admissible high and low level for the level upstream of the dams has to be defined. These ratings would take into account the needs for navigation, i.e. the minimum draught for ships below bridges and the channel depth for ship draught.

Figure 13: The French part of the river Moselle (VNF 2022)

Responsibilities/tasks of the inland navigation infrastructure provider in France in relation to the CRISTAL pilot

VNF oversees to

- Regulate water levels
- Guarantee navigability for recreational navigation
- Guarantee navigability for commercial shipping cargo ships
- Management of infrastructure
- Ensuring the reliability of the infrastructure at a given level of service

Current status and existing challenges:

The main issues currently faced in the Moselle and Seine area include the following:

- interruptions can have serious economic consequences, especially for heavy goods traffic since daily delay penalties are very high. This becomes an even bigger issue when heavy goods traffic is more often interrupted;
- Drifts (e.g. due to flooding) as a cause of traffic disruption;
- While there is already a certain amount of data available, since many sensors are already installed on the infrastructures, real time integration and decision making could be improved. That is why VNF is

working on the issue of connected objects (IOT) and the development of a digital map, and CRISTAL could make it possible to contribute to complete this digitalisation of infrastructures;

- it is expected that climate change reasoned events will cause interruptions to traffic, and that difficulties will arise on certain structures;
- regarding autonomous vessels, there is currently no solution in place for them to pass through locks. Any decision regarding the technological solution which systems are put onto the vessel and which into the infrastructure are however pending.

Status and existing challenges regarding the Moselle Region

- On the Moselle, variations in water flow have been observed for the last 5 years, there was 1 interruption in traffic: proof of an ongoing disruption.
- Economic consequences observed on the economic actors linked to the reserved flow: possible stop of the production of factories which can no longer supply themselves with water.
- Low water problems on the routes and network for smaller vessels with repercussions on the wide-gauge network.
- Possible future consequences for the tourism sector.
- Modelling studies have been done on the downstream flow of the Moselle with CEREMA (hydraulic management): possibility of using this study for the project.

Innovations foreseen to mitigate the currently experienced issues include:

- Tools to anticipate extreme weather events.
- More sensors on the network and further work on the modelling, including also more data, to refine the granularity of the existing water flow model.
- Establish predictive water flow models that support help decision-making.
- Tools for predictive infrastructure maintenance.
- Tools to predict drifts which also allow interconnection with other actors.

French pilot site tasks

So the objectives of the French pilot in CRISTAL include

- Tools to anticipate extreme weather events ;
- More sensors on the network and further work on the modelling, including also more data, to refine the granularity of the model ;(->WP2)
- Establish predictive models that support help decision-making (->WP5);
- Tools for predictive infrastructure maintenance (->WP5);;
- Tools to predict drifts which also allow interconnection with other actors ((->WP5)
- Collection and exchange of river freight data on the European network to support planning of the transport and early information of partners within the transport chain as a possible input to WP3

Actions include

- Collect and exchange river freight data on the European network
- Install sensors on Seine aval to connect them with the European information systems
- Develop smart buoys on Moselle
- Demonstrate lock radar inspection on Moselle (->WP5)

3.3. The Italian pilot site at the river Po

Inland navigation in Northern Italy develops within and around the natural course of the river Po. This territory, which is flat and includes four different regions, is also characterised by a network of artificial and natural canals, historically used to transport goods and people but, until today, exploited only to a rather limited extent, especially for the transport of goods.

In the context of this area of high economic dynamism, the inland waterway mode of transport, if adapted in terms of infrastructure and transport in an environmentally sustainable manner, could reduce the frequent congestion of motorways and railways and make a significant contribution to the reduction of harmful emissions in the sector.

The transport network and infrastructure for inland waterways in Northern Italy and the Northern Adriatic consists of (moving progressively from west to east along the Po Valley)

- the inland ports of Cremona, Mantua, Rovigo, Boretto, Ferrara and Porto Nogaro (and other public and private docks along the waterway)
- the Po River and the Mantua-Adriatic Sea Canal, i.e. the two main waterways that synergistically connect the sea to the heart of the Po Valley, with an east-west relationship, where the inland ports are located;
- the Venice Lagoon, the Po-Brondolo canal and the Ferrara waterway, which connect the major waterways to the seaports with a north-south trend;
- the North Adriatic Sea ports, such as Ravenna, Chioggia, Venice, Monfalcone and Trieste.

This Network constitutes the "Padano-Veneto Waterway System", defined by the Decree of the Ministry of Transport and Navigation no. 759 of 25/06/92, provided for by Law no. 380/90; the System has an extension of 987.5 Km (of which 601 usable for commercial purposes) and includes the following waterways

- the Po River from Piacenza to Porto Tolle: 312 km (near the mouth)
- the first section of the MI-CR-PO Canal (to Pizzighettone): 14 km
- the Mincio River from Mantua to the Po (via Governolo): 20 km;
- the Fissero Canal-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante (incile): 117 km;
- the Po-Brondolo-Laguna Veneta Canal: 19 km;
- the Po di Levante: 19 km;
- the Venetian Lagoon (from Chioggia to Venice): 30 km;
- the Ferrara Waterway (Pontelagoscuro-Porto Garibaldi): 70 km;
- the Aussa-Corno Canal: 4 km

The connection between the navigable canals of the Po Valley and the Aussa Corno Canal is guaranteed not only by the presence of the Venetian Lagoon, but also by the marine strip immediately facing the coastline, which is normatively classified as an inland water line by Law 16/2000. In addition, since March 2018, another 37 kilometres of waterway have been included in the network, by virtue of the construction of the new Isola Serafini lock, which has made the Po navigable again from the Adriatic to Piacenza, thus making an important contribution to the reduction of road transport, to the improvement of traffic and air quality, as well as to a likely increase in merchant traffic. Furthermore, the Cremona-Milan canal, which

today only extends as far as Pizzighettone (14 km), may in the future be an important and further extension of the waterway system, reaching as far as Truccazzano, thus serving the industrial areas of the Milanese hinterland.

The main commercial ports along the Po river shaft, of Cremona, Mantua, Revere and Ostiglia, the Boretto, Piacenza, Ferrara and Rovigo river basins, are ports of particular strategic interest in the regional planning of inland waterway transport in Lombardy, Emilia Romagna and Veneto.

Lastly, along the Po Valley-Veneto Waterway System there are numerous other ports and tourist landings, as well as a fair number of private quays for commercial use.

There are also the following 'basins'(1): Isola Serafini, Cremona, Governolo and San Leone, Valdaro, Pontelagoscuro, Volta Grimana, as well as three other basins along the Ferrara waterway and five basins

Figure 14: The Po river system (Uniontrasporti 2022)

The Po Valley-Veneto Waterway System, due to its strategic importance, has been included for years in the Trans-European Waterway Network, with Decision no. 1692/96/EC of 23/07/96.

On the 2011 Revision of the Trans-European Transport Networks (TEN-T), the Inland Navigation Network of European Significance was also redefined; the relative details for Italy can be found in Chapter XI (Trans-European Transport Networks TEN-T) of this and previous editions of the Account.

However, due to the geographic and morphological conformation of the Italian territory and the infrastructural deficiencies that limit the development of inland navigation, as well as the economic crisis of recent years that has reduced the number of companies operating in the sector, inland waterway transport is still far from becoming a real alternative to traditional road, rail and air carriers. Nevertheless, inland navigation holds a set of specialised trades with added value, such as the transport of large industrial equipment, which is almost always incompatible with road and rail modes, not to mention the

undoubted advantages in terms of safety and high transport capacity for liquid chemicals as well as hazardous materials.

The negative consequences on the economy of the Covid-19 pandemic have, unfortunately, also significantly affected the inland shipping sector, making it necessary to start again, as soon as possible, with new designs for sustainable development.

Responsibilities and tasks of the inland navigation infrastructure provider in Italy in relation to the CRISTAL pilot

For Italy the Infrastructure Operators are AIPo and Infrastrutture Venete. Since 2010, the Interregional Agency for the Po River (Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po A.I.Po, formerly ARNI) has been in charge of coordinating the activities between the different Regions watered by the great Italian navigable river, as well as of important operational activities consisting in infrastructure maintenance, service management, port control and surveillance, rescue, and the protection and promotion of the Po-Veneto Waterway System as a whole.

Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l. manages the region's railway and inland navigation infrastructures, began operations on 1 January 2020 on behalf of the Veneto Region. In fact, by Regional Law No. 40 of 14 November 2018, the Veneto Region ordered the corporate demerger of Sistemi Territoriali Spa, transferring to Infrastrutture Venete Srl the management competences of the inland navigation and railway infrastructures, as well as the competences relating to the management of Local Public Transport by rail throughout the regional territory.

Italian pilot site tasks

Overall, the Italian pilot aims at improving the assets management of the inland waterways' infrastructure through an overall digitalization of the logistic and of the people transport services

- making use of digital technologies (including the digital twin),
- while ensuring biodiversity and environmental impacts,
- green energy procurement and
- resilience certification.
- The deployment of the COPERNICUS climate services for the climate model is planned.

More precisely, as far as the river Po pilot, the sections where Italian pilot identified technologies will be tested:

- Fiber optic sensor, hydraulic model and smart daily report in support of shippers and Port Authorities (bulletin): from Cremona to “foce Mincio” (Mincio mouth).
- Feasibility study for the realization of a network of cold iron facilities: along the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbionco – Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal

Furthermore, an overall innovation and improvement of the governance process of the “River Po Corridor management”, supporting for route planning, voyage planning, transport, and traffic management,

securing (contingency management) the supply for goods for the relevant supply chain and for tourism management is aimed at.

All these measures shall lead to a reduction of the CO₂-footprint of the river management services.

3.4. The Polish pilot site at the rivers Vistula and Odra

The transport function of inland waterways is mainly the result of the adaptation of the structural parameters of the river fleet to the parameters of the waterway. The division of inland waterways in Poland into classes, adapted to the standards in force in the EU countries, was defined in the Regulation of the Council of Ministers on the classification of inland waterways.

International class waterways (class IV and higher), allowing the operation of self-propelled barges of up to 1,500 tonnes and pushed convoys of up to 1,450 tonnes, meet about 5.5% of their length (205.9 km) in Poland. The remaining inland waterways meet the technical requirements specified as being of regional importance.

However, from the point of view of the vessels operating in Poland, the existing technical class of the waterways is not the main barrier to their transport use. This is because the vessels were constructed in the 1960s taking into account the existing navigation conditions on the national waterways. More than 70% of Poland's fleet consists of pushed barges with an average tonnage of 450 tonnes. In the group of the pushed fleet, 65% are vessels of up to 500 tonnes. These vessels can therefore be operated even under Class II waterway technical conditions. This means, therefore, that 1678.1 km of inland waterways in Poland (44.5%) are formally accessible this fleet.

Figure 15: Maps of the river systems Odra and Vistula (Wikipedia 2022)

Poland's waterways are however less accessible to self-propelled barges, which account for 30% of the total fleet. These are barges with an average tonnage of 780 tonnes, with the load capacity of 60% of self-propelled vessels between 650 and 1500 tonnes. Only a fraction of this fleet can be operated in at least technical class III conditions, and only 17% of inland waterways recognised as navigable meet this requirement. In contrast, barges of 1,500 tonnes can be operated under international waterway class conditions, which, as already mentioned, represent only 5.5% of the length of waterways recognised as navigable. (Eurostat 2022)

Therefore, the majority of cargo transport in Poland is carried out using unpowered barges. In the long term, however, there is a trend towards a decrease in the importance of this group of vessels in the realisation of transport. In 2005, the share of self-propelled barges in total carriage was 90%, in 2010. - 87%, and in 2021. - almost 78%. Self-propelled barges are more frequently used in international than in domestic carriage. In 2010, 28% of international haulage and only 0.2% of domestic haulage was carried out using self-propelled barges. In 2021, the share of the self-propelled fleet in international haulage increased to 33% and in domestic haulage to almost 23%. (Eurostat 2002)

Many years neglecting the development and maintenance of inland waterways have resulted in numerous transit depth restrictions on many sections, making freight navigation difficult or even impossible. Most such restrictions are on the lower Vistula, the free-flowing Oder, the border Oder and the Gliwice Canal. Thus, even though formally these sections are classified in a certain technical class, these parameters (especially with regard to transit depth) are not guaranteed by the infrastructure manager. Under these conditions, it is very difficult to achieve ship draughts even at a level that determines the minimum profitability of freight transport.

As a result, a long-term trend is observed in Poland:

- decreasing freight volumes on inland waterways,
- the decreasing share of inland shipping in the branch distribution of transport tasks,
- narrowing the spatial market for freight transport on inland waterways,
- narrowing the conduit market to serve a narrow group of loads,
- the declining propensity of inland waterway shipowners to develop the river fleet.

A decline in cargo transport has been observed in Poland since 1980, when transport of 22 million tonnes was recorded.² In 2010, 2.8 million tonnes were transported by inland waterway in Poland. By 2014, these transports were increasing, reaching 5.9 million tonnes. In the following years they decreased, and in 2021 they reached 2.1 million tonnes. A similar trend was observed for domestic transport³. In 2010, domestic haulage stood at 1.5 million tonnes, rising to 4.8 million tonnes in 2014. They decreased in the following

² Statistics on freight transport on the EU inland waterway network are recorded according to the 'territoriality principle'. This means that each country reports the loading, unloading and movements of goods that take place on its territory, irrespective of the country of origin of the enterprises or the place of first loading and final unloading.

³ Domestic inland waterway transport is transport between two ports on Polish territory, regardless of the nationality of the vessel.

years and amounted to 1.7 million tonnes in 2021. International shipments have shown a steady downward trend since 2010. They stood at 1.3 million tonnes in 2010 and 0.4 million tonnes in 2021.⁴

The highest share of inland waterway transport in the sectoral breakdown of freight transport (road, rail and inland waterway transport = 100%) in terms of tonnes transported was recorded in Poland between 1980 and 1990. During this period the share was 0.8%. Between 1995 and 2005, this share decreased to 0.7%. In the following years, this share also decreased, reaching 0.3% in 2010 and 0.2% in 2021.

In terms of transport work, on the other hand, the highest share of inland shipping in the branch distribution was recorded in Poland in 1970 (1.9%). In the following years, this share also decreased. Between 2010 and 2021, the share of inland waterway transport in inland transport work will decrease from 0.4% in 2010 to 0.1% in 2021.

Transit depth restriction points on many sections prevent long-distance transport. As a result, domestic inland waterway transport in Poland is characterised by its local character. In the period 2010-2021 on the Odra waterway, transport was carried out only on the lower section and on the upper channelised Odra. On the other sections of the Odra and on the Vistula they are only sporadic or not carried out at all.

Local transport up to 49 km in 2000 accounted for 60% of domestic inland waterway transport in Poland, and the average transport distance of 1 tonne in this distance zone was 6 km. In 2005, the share of transport up to 49 km was 73%, in 2010. - 63%. The average distance of carriage of 1 tonne in this distance zone in 2005 was 7 km, in 2010. - 9 km. In 2021, the share of domestic haulage up to 49 km was 69% and the average haulage distance of 1 tonne in this distance zone fell to around 5 km.

The local nature of transport is reflected in the specific cargo structure of transport. Domestic inland waterway transport in Poland is mainly concentrated on cargoes included, according to the NTS 2007 classification, in the cargo group classified as 03 - metal ores and other mining and quarrying products; peat; uranium and thorium. The share of this cargo group in inland waterway transport in 2010 was 41%, in 2015. - 61%, and in 2021. - 51%. Inland navigation in Poland is however not used for the carriage of any metal ores. Hence, almost 100% of transport within this cargo group is related to the transport of construction materials (Stone, sand, gravel, clay, peat and other mining and quarrying products). For the most part, these are transports of aggregates extracted from the riverbed, which are the exclusive sphere of activity of this branch of transport.

The second position in the cargo structure of transport by waterways in Poland is occupied by cargo classified as coal, lignite, crude oil and natural gas (Coal and lignite; crude petroleum and natural gas). Between 2010 and 2021, the share of this cargo group in total transport showed a decreasing trend. In 2010, it accounted for 33% and in 2021. - 23% of total freight carried by this mode of transport. More activity has been shown by this branch of transport, especially since 2015, in the carriage of cargoes classified in the cargo group as Coke and refined petroleum products. However, the share of this cargo group in total transport between 2015 and 2021 has decreased from 15% to 11%.

Numerous limiting transit depths on the inland waterway network have contributed to a significant deterioration of the operating conditions for inland waterway transport in Poland. Hence, shipowners in

⁴ International inland waterways transport comprises transport between two ports, one port being on the territory of Poland and the other on the territory of another country

Poland show no inclination to develop inland waterway rolling stock. Between 2010 and 2021, the number of self-propelled barges decreased by 10%, non-self-propelled barges by as much as 66% and pushers by 54%. The inland waterway fleet in Poland is largely decapitalised. At present, barges (motorised and not self-propelled) that were built after 1990 account for only 1.6% of their total number. A similar situation exists in the group of pushers. The share of vessels that were built after 1990 in their total number is currently 4.2%. Thus, the exploitation of inland waterway rolling stock in Poland is only possible thanks to permanent repairs.

These trends should not discourage efforts to increase the role of inland waterway transport in freight transport in Poland. Increasing the transport use of inland waterways should be seen as one of the ways to shape sustainable transport. These actions are part of the implementation of the European Green Deal concept. Indeed, this concept states that "First and foremost, the role of rail and inland waterways in inland freight transport should be significantly increased".

Poland has a considerable length of inland waterways recognised as navigable (3768 km). A longer waterway network is only found in Germany, Finland, France and the Netherlands. Poland also has one of the highest waterway density rates in Europe. Failure to use this potential, in the light of growing transport needs and the need to curb unfavourable climate change, would mean exacerbating the problems associated with the dynamic development of road transport (emissions, congestion). The increasing role of inland waterway transport in the branch division of transport tasks in the transport system in Poland therefore means a necessity:

- the guarantee by the infrastructure manager of stable navigational conditions on inland waterways.
- restoration by the waterway manager of the technical parameters (in particular with regard to transit depth) on road sections where they do not comply with the class formally assigned to the section.
- the renewal of river rolling stock.

Responsibilities and tasks of the inland navigation infrastructure provider in Poland in relation to the CRISTAL pilot

According to the current legal status, the policy on the development (construction, reconstruction, modernisation) of inland waterways is jointly shaped by the minister in charge of water management and the minister in charge of inland navigation. Currently in Poland the functions of these ministries are performed under one entity - the Ministry of Infrastructure (Journal of Laws 2020, item 1745).

Maintenance of inland waterways, on the other hand, is the direct responsibility of the State Water Management Company Wody Polskie and, at the level of water regions, of the Regional Water Management Boards (RZGW) (Water Law, Dz.U. 2021 item 2233). There are three divisions within the organisational structure of RZGW:

- flood and drought protection division,
- water services division,
- water environment management division.

The tasks of the Flood and Drought Protection division are related to the planning and implementation of flood protection investments and the provision of water for agriculture.

The Water Services Division is responsible for matters relating to water use, including inland navigation, energy, industry, tourism and recreation. The tasks of this division include, among others:

- issuing of water permits (navigation on inland waterways, towing and timber floating do not require a water permit or water notification) ,
- the collection of charges for the use, owned by the State, of inland waterways or sections thereof and hydrotechnical facilities,
- cooperation with the competent authorities regarding inland waterways,
- handling matters related to the tourist use of water,
- handling matters concerning fisheries management,
- conducting matters related to hydropower, regarding hydroelectric power plants owned by the State and other entities,
- ongoing cooperation with water users, including: local authorities, water users, water companies (Wody Polskie 2022) .

The inland waterway manager does not report any problems re. conflicting uses of inland waterways between any users. Regulatory developments, water stages, reservoirs are inherently multifunctional.

The Water Environment Management Division is responsible for the implementation of EU directives and for matters relating to protected areas. These specific tasks include:

- carrying out maintenance work (removal of obstacles from the riverbed, repair and maintenance of structures, installation and maintenance of navigational markings);
- to provide information on the current status and obstructions of inland waterways by means of navigational information messages,
- issuing notices of closure and opening of waterways to inland navigation⁵.

The responsibility of the Regional Water Management Authority does not directly imply an obligation to maintain a technical class on waterways, as stipulated in the Regulation on the Classification of Inland Waterways. In free-flowing river sections, the water level depends on the hydrological and meteorological conditions throughout the catchment area and is not controlled by water facilities. In contrast, measures to ensure the required transit depth are possible regarding water reservoirs and navigable channels, e.g: Włocławek Water Reservoir, Zegrzyńskie Lake and Żerański Canal.

The failure to comply with the applicable classes on many road sections is of a long-standing nature in Poland. This situation, as previously stated, severely restricts the possibility of navigating especially on long-distance routes.

Current experience shows that waterway closure notices completely prevent all types of vessels from navigating. In this situation, even vessels with smaller technical characteristics cannot use the waterway, even with appropriate safety conditions.

⁵ According to RZGW

The periods when waterways are not marked for too long are also a problem. There are objective situations in which the waterway administration is forced to remove navigational markings in the waterway (high tide, passage of ice floes). However, in practice, the periods when markings have been taken off the route are much longer than the actual duration of the phenomena preventing navigation would suggest. Furthermore, the absence of markings should not completely restrict navigation, under proper safety conditions and under the carrier's own responsibility. It should therefore be incumbent on the waterway authority to issue notices of the sections where navigation markings have been temporarily removed. These notices should also include information on the current navigational conditions on these sections.

The limited capacity and navigability of the inland waterways associated with years of neglect of infrastructure maintenance and the increase of extreme weather events (drought, heavy rain) require a new approach to the use of inland waterways in supply chains. Therefore, within the framework of WP9 of the CRISTAL project, logistics models will be created for different cargo groups allowing the use of inland waterways in the current state of infrastructure, while gradually adapting logistics chains to shift volumes towards inland waterways. The models developed, will be verified through the implementation of pilot cruises on the Vistula and Odra. The use of IoT and special buoys providing information on navigational conditions will allow IWT-based supply chains to become more flexible and react quickly to changing navigational conditions (e.g. closure of shipping lanes).

Polish pilot site tasks

The pilot and the models developed will be complemented by a series of socio-economic surveys aimed not only at understanding the attitude of the public (residents, businesses, NGOs) towards IWT, but also at raising awareness of the environment regarding the operation of IWT and its impact on the environment. So, the overall goal is to enable inland waterway transport connections through setting up the new IWT services for different types of cargo (unitized-containerized, break-bulk and dry bulk) under possibly permanent unfortunate navigation conditions. Any necessary infrastructure improvement would be a subject of a long-term perspective (more than 25 years) and enforces adoption to current disruptions (low water level, prohibited or limited navigability during winter periods and at nights, missing RIS and changing hydrology) for navigation.

From the perspective of a transport network the focus will be given to the optimization of supply chains towards the achievement of co-modal transport services within a well synchronized, smart and seamless network, supported by Inland Waterway Transport for shippers or forwarders via the developments in WP3. It will be executed by elaboration of new business and logistics models of IWT and implementation of IoT technology to enable monitoring of cargo & vessels/barges location and other parameters increasing its modal share.

Intelligent buoys system provided for demo pilots will provide a set of measurements describing the sailing conditions (draught, bridge clearance, wind etc) to make a decision to run a IW voyage or to use alternative transport mean (road or rail). Furthermore, intelligent connection between buoys and barges will allow to monitor barge ETA and warn the supply chain management party to launch emergency procedures to keep proper goods flow in case of delay.

Three pilots will be performed on Vistula River with different type of cargo (containersied, dry bulk, general cargo). All of them will start/finish at internal Port of Gdansk (sea terminals). Pilot tests will also give a good ground to develop a tariff for IW barges service at port terminals, as currently such document and terms and conditions for such operations does not exist.

First sketches indicated two available delivery/loading locations on the hinterland. First one, Chelмно river quay – for delivery of containerised and bulk cargo. Second location was found in Wloclawek – quay at the chemical enterprise’s facility where the vessel will load with fertilizers stuffed in bigbag units. Different types of cargo may require use of different barge type configurations, such as platform (pontoon) or hopper barge.

Figure 16: Segment of the Vistula (Wisla) river for the Polish test site Source: University of Gdansk

Fourth pilot will be launched in full market conditions to compare the service between IWT, rail, and road transport. Such pilot environment is available to perform on international waterways between port of Antwerp or Duisburg and Gliwice with use of Odra River. The pilot will finish at tri-modal terminal in IW port in Gliwice, southern Poland.

Previously launched IWW pilot projects (Interreg EMMA Extension) showed serious limitations at inland waterways reloading infrastructure. CRISTAL pilots should provide a list of available locations and short guideline with minimum infra and suprastructure requirements including storage yards, reloading equipment,

The main goals for Polish pilots are to:

- develop a supply chain model and define the new services in the existing port terminals,
- update a list of locations with potential as reloading infrastructure and give the minimum requirements for IWT reloading facilities
- develop business and logistics models implementing IWT as important hinterland transport mean plotted into existing supply chains
- carry out 4 demonstrations of different cargo transport, as well as of different legal conditions (national vs. international),

- develop, implement and test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys system,
- study the socio-economic importance of inland waterways in the region.
-

All above goals should help the logistics market to adapt IWW into their supply network and lead to IWW transport development in limited infrastructure and extreme weather conditions.

3.5. Critical issues, requirements and expectations in the three pilots

Task 1.1 developed a questionnaire, which was provided to the infrastructure operators. The questionnaire is to be found in the annex.

The questionnaire was dedicated only to the infrastructure providers only. That should be considered when reading the answers. Within the domain of infrastructure management, transport quality issues related to other market participants may fall short. The questionnaire had the following goals

- Collect information about the main issues in operation like contractual obligations, internal or external KPIs, recorded disturbances in operations, capacity, infrastructure maintenance challenges, impact of climate change
- Create an overview about IT systems in use and IT systems and processes required for a better infrastructure resilience

Table 3: Contractual obligations

Contractual obligations of infrastructure operator	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) Infrastrutture Venete	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
	Guarantee navigability for recreational navigation Guarantee navigability for commercial shipping cargo ships Management of infrastructure	Management of infrastructure	Regulate water levels (only in Canalbianco river) Guarantee navigability for recreational navigation Guarantee navigability for commercial shipping cargo ships	

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

	Ensuring the reliability of the infrastructure at a given level of service		Ensuring accessibility to the infrastructure	
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Table 4: Issues with a significant impact re. the application of the different technologies in your pilot site

Issues	France (seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
Accessibility	Defined service levels, maintenance program (validated 2 years in advance) with navigation stop level of service (hours, gauge)	The accessibility is only restricted as a function of low water levels and depending on vessels draft. There is no agreed service level of accessibility.	Access is free. Physical accessibility to the waterway is limited to vessels of maximum size about 110 m x 11 m x 3.5 m draft. Infrastrutture Venete is ISO 9001 and 45001 certified. There is also the regulation of signs and inland waterways published in the Official Bulletin of the Veneto Region no. 125 of 12/24/2002. All navigation locks are operated remotely free of charge 24/7.	
Preventive or Predictive Maintenance	Yes	No answer	Yes, IV already performs preventive maintenance on the plants based on ISO 9001 procedures.	
Reliability of transport services	No, since agreement between stakeholders	Yes	No	
Navigability	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Waterway infrastructure resilience	Yes . At this point VNF inland waterways are considered resilient.	No	No	

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

Issues	France (seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
Coordination of Passenger and freight transports	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Modal split	Yes	No	Yes	
Intermodal transport	No	No	Yes	
Synchronisation of services / Waiting times in transport hubs	No	No	Yes	
Emissions and pollutions	No	No	Yes	
Collaboration among actors	No	No	No	
Overall corridor transit time	No	No	No	

Table 5: Necessity of a corridor management system

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
C7. In your opinion, do transport operators/ the users have sufficient resources in terms of the accessibility of alternative means of transportation in times of closure of the IWW segment?	No answer	Yes, they usually shift to road or railway transport services.	No, they don't, but they can use the Po River as an alternative to the Canalbianco.	

Table 6: Ports in the IWT segments

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
C8. Are there currently any established interfaces (e.g. IWW port with rail connection) with other modes of transport (road, rail) in the segment of inland waterway(s) you are responsible for? If yes, please list them	Haropa (Le Havre, Rouen, Paris), Moselle ports	Mantua and Cremona ports are linked to the railway system as to the road system. Other minor docks are linked to the road system as well.	Port of Mantua and Interport of Rovigo. At the Interport of Rovigo, in addition to the interface with road traffic, there is a railway yard.	

Table 7: Impact of Climate Change

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
C10. Do you regard climate change as a main driver of future accessibility / reliability / navigability issues? Is it presently the case or is that an expectation for the future?	Requirement for more information for the future: local water needs and local water resources in particular	Climate change is a main driver of future accessibility and for the Po river and northern Italy inland waterway system is already the case	Climate change affects whether water levels are too low or too high based on weather events. Since all systems are controlled remotely there could be problems in case of lightning.	
E4. Do you regard climate change as a main driver of future infrastructure maintenance demand? Is it presently the case or is that an expectation for the future?	No answer	Climate change has already an impact on maintenance demand, but it's not a main driver. For the Po river an important driver is the sediment loss which has caused the lowering of the river bed.	We think it's an expectation for the future.	

Table 8: Capacity

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
D1. Theoretical capacity of the waterway segment	No answer	Capacity is for sure underutilised but there are no data available	About 3.500 barges with tugs up to 1,500-2,000 tons each. It currently sails about 1 barge per week.	

Table 9: Available structural drawings and/or data about constructive and geometrical characteristics of the infrastructures that you manage

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
<p>E2. Do you have structural drawings and/or data about constructive and geometrical characteristics of the infrastructures that you manage? Any structured forms procedure for periodically assessing the state of maintenance? E.g. a digitised 3D model or BIM (Building Information Modelling)?</p>	<p>Yes National data base (BDO : base de données ouvrages) with regular inspection</p>	<p>Executive design of groynes; DEM of the Po river (including 3D bathymetry)</p>	<p>Yes, structural drawings and/or data about constructive and geometrical characteristics of the infrastructures that we manage. No digitised 3D model or BIM (Building Information Modelling) yet.</p>	

Table 10: IT systems in place

	France (seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
C3. Are there currently any functional operational digital platforms in the segment of inland waterway(s) you are responsible for? If yes, which are the digital services offered (please list them) and who is the manager of this/these platform(s)?	EURIS: European group	<p>RIS Italy - The system is open for operators only. There used to be a RIS website (https://www.ris-italy.com/) which can be reached through the AIPO website (agenziapo.it).</p> <p>AIPO manages an online informative system that reports on hydrographic levels (https://www.agenziapo.it/content/monitoraggio-idrografico-0)</p>	<p>RIS II - Study for standard enhancement and interconnection of national systems of RIS-Italy. Unfortunately the RIS system is ready but not yet operational as the RIS directive must be implemented by the Ministry. Cartographic map, notices to mariners, requests for passage to the locks The manager of this/these platform(s) are Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l. and AIPO.</p> <p>Water level sensors connected to a company server / analogue sensors connected with PLC for process control / every minute</p> <p>HMI (Human Machine Interface) systems implemented for the management of navigation locks and hydraulic barriers. All navigation locks and hydraulic barriers are managed remotely with video surveillance via SCADA with radio link or connection from provider.</p>	None

Table 11: Expectations and requirements towards the technology developments in CRISTAL

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
Sensors	<p>Need CRISTAL sensors for maintenance and use of harbour quay</p> <p>SHM only if costs reasonable</p>	<p>Webcams are not included in the "CRISTAL sensors data provision", but AiPo doesn't have any webcam/livecam along the Po river and on bridges, that could be useful to monitor the river itself, and, for example, the quantity and type of floating debris.</p> <p>Fiber optic sensors that should be used on the Po river pilot should be able to measure variations in riverbed sediment thickness. Buoys are not foreseen for the Po river pilot, but they could demonstrate useful to monitor navigation in the Po river between the ports of Mantua and Cremona , even for touristic purpose.</p>		Inclusion of buoys sensors into OIT services for IWT
Data acquisition system	Benchmark first required	In theory, the RIS-Italy is already a well-developed data acquisition system	Existing Analyzer Zenon Copadata system.	

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
Dashboards or Apps	Yes, Navigability dashboard and Apps		Yes, desired	
Digital Twin functional requirements	Test for automation and distant operation	Shallow waters forecast Use the outputs of the mobile-bed hydraulic model to have forecasts on water depths (the mobile-bed hydraulic model will be probably our digital twin component)	Reliability of the acquired data historical data management real-time management of alarms	
Digital Twin non-functional requirements	Usability	If we consider the river as part of the navigation infrastructure, then the digital twin could be useful in supporting the planning of dredging operations (which are then intended as river infrastructure maintenance). Apart from this, our digital twin would be more useful to make as trouble-free as possible traffic operations.	Controlled data access management ease of use by the operator possibility of remote intervention	
Digital twin as a good tool to test and plan for the	No answer	Yes, we will use the outputs of the mobile-bed hydraulic model to have forecasts on	Yes, we do. We hope to get reliable monitoring of more	

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
operation of the facilities?		water depths (the mobile-bed hydraulic model will be probably our digital twin component	infrastructure parameters.	
Concrete wall inspection device functional requirements	Identify and position the reinforced concrete reinforcements in the locks without technical documentation Locate leaks, cracks, and cavities	No	We don't know the functionality of concrete walls inspection device. We have to study this device	
Integration of all traffic related Apps with RIS	Mandatory	Now the integration with existing RIS-Italy system is desirable and not mandatory, until the RIS directive is not taken into national legislation. We would like to implement the use of the RIS in the frame of the CRISTAL project.		
synchro-modal corridor management system		No benefit from the development of such a system. Port authorities maybe would have some	Surely an infrastructure monitoring system helps all operators to know its status in real time.	
F11. KPIs To what extent			Some significant KPIs could be:	

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
would data about the navigability (intelligent buoys for controlled waterways or Fiber Optic sensors for free-flowing waterways) and preventive maintenance sensors (I.e. inspection radar) be processed and synthesised into meaningful KPIs that can enrich actual data? Do you have any proposal for KPIs?			hydraulic level reading, hydraulic gate opening degree reading, hydraulic gate lifting system load status reading	
F12. Without any additional data and tools, how is planning carried out today in terms of expected extreme weather events and the resulting low or high water levels? How do you do it?		We have modelling chains to forecast discharges and hydrometric levels	The current system requires each hydraulic barrier to maintain a certain level of navigation water upstream of it. The gates move automatically in order to guarantee this upstream level in each hydraulic support. Canalbianco is a regulated artificial canal, and as such, it is easier to	

	France (Seine and Moselle)	Italy (Po) AiPo	Italy (Po) IV	Poland (Vistula and Odra)
			manage adverse atmospheric events. The management of the last stretch of the canal in direct contact with the sea is more difficult, since, in the event of scirocco wind and high tide, there can be repercussions on navigation up to about 30 km from the sea.	

To conclude: These answers of the infrastructure authorities show the heterogenous approach and framework conditions in the three pilots. The answers regarding expectations and possible use of the technology developments in CRISTAL should however not be taken too literally. While the contractual tasks of these actors may not include that e.g. the transport quality that is achieved by barge operators is of their concern, the CRISTAL consortium however intends to see the broader picture of IWT logistics, involving all stakeholders for the greater whole of the system.

4. Evaluation framework for CRISTAL technologies

The evaluation framework presented in the following chapter aims to assess the impact of the CRISTAL technologies to be applied in the three river pilots, taking into account the perspective of the different stakeholders involved (operators, users etc.). To fulfil this objective different evaluation instruments and tools are presented including **tools for impact** and **vulnerability analysis** as well as **tools for financial analysis**. In particular, the framework provides the grounds for a multidimensional sustainable technology assessment including **resource availability**, **environmental impacts**, **logistic optimisation**, **economic efficiency** and **social impacts**. The framework is common for all three pilot sites with a few alternative options available, when possible, in case of lack of data or failure to meet certain criteria. The evaluation framework is adapted from the FENIX Common Evaluation Framework, a six-step approach developed for impact evaluation of digital services implementation in Transport and Logistics operations. The following Figure 17 outlines the six steps of the evaluation framework methodology adjusted to fit the evaluation purpose of the activities of the river pilots within CRISTAL project.

Figure 17: The 6-step evaluation framework for river pilots (adapted from FENIX⁶)

Steps 1-4 refer to horizontal processes that gather information and data, Step 5 is applied independently for each evaluation method and Step 6 proves the impact of the pilots. Each step will be performed by each one of the three river pilots. The following Table 12 specifies what the framework evaluates, how, when and who performs the evaluation activities.

⁶ <https://fenix-network.eu/>

Table 12: Boundaries of the evaluation framework

What is evaluated	The impact of the technologies and solutions that are developed in the context of the three pilots in Italy, France and Poland
How it is evaluated	Using the evaluation framework and the different methodologies and tools included
When it is evaluated	Following the completion of the river pilots, in combination with results and data gathered from a baseline scenario
Who performs the evaluation	The representative of each pilot site (evaluation leader) in collaboration with operators and project partners

The framework aims to assess the overall impact of the different technologies and solutions that will be developed and tested in the three pilot sites, such as Fiber Optic Sensing, Tunnel inspection technology, Intelligent Buoy System, Toolbox for synchro-modal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation, Corridor visibility open data platform, CIPcast DSS Early detection systems and alert, etc.

The evaluation framework incorporates elements of the different tasks outlined in WP10 regarding the Validation Framework. In particular, Task 10.4 regarding Sustainability Validation, can be performed by implementing the suggested framework presented hereby. The framework also touches upon some aspects of technology and operational performance evaluation, however those will be evaluated in detail in the respective tasks of WP10.

Step 1: Expected impacts

In this section, the expected impact areas of the river pilots are identified. Following a review of the project objectives, the objectives of pilots together with guidance from relevant literature and projects, the areas of expected impacts are identified as shown in Table 13: Objectives of pilots and expected impact areas. The areas of expected impacts are grouped based on the sustainability triple bottom line; economy, environment, and society (Ayfantopoulou et al., 2022). It is noted that, in some cases, the expected impacts (and respective indicators) may fit to more than one dimension, since the three dimensions are interrelated, and their targets overlap.

Table 13: Objectives of pilots and expected impact areas

Objectives	Expected Impact Area
ECONOMIC	
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.	Navigability of inland waterways
Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	Land/sea/infrastructure resilience
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	Visibility of shipments & Logistics optimisation
Improve reliability to 80% of cases being on-time.	Reliability of shipments
Advance the Physical Internet, synchronise intermodal services between modes and with shippers, align equipment and services on corridors and hubs and integrate these into networks.	Physical Internet and Synchromodality
Develop a resilient, more competitive and more entrepreneurial regional inland waterways transport and logistic economy	Economic efficiency
ENVIRONMENTAL	
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift	Share of inland water transport in the modal split
Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	Recycled materials
Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.	Emissions and Soil/water pollution
SOCIAL	
Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.	Collaboration among stakeholders / Governance models
Ensure navigation facilitation and safety, increase safety and security of the transport system, for passengers and freight.	Safety
Synchromodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system.	Intermodal / multimodal transportation
Enhance the socio-economic importance of inland waterways	Perception of inland navigation

Step 2: Definition of targets and identification of indicators

For each one of the expected impact areas as those specified in Table 13, a target is set which derives either from the project objectives as described in the Grant Agreement or the desired outcome of pilots. The desired outcome of pilots will be confirmed at a later stage depending on the needs and challenges of each pilot (marked as 'TBD' in Table 14). The targets can be specified based on the SMART criteria (Doran, 1981):

- **Specific** – targeted to a specific area for improvement
- **Measurable** – quantified indicators of progress
- **Achievable** – realistic and attainable
- **Relevant** – aligned with results that can realistically be achieved given available resources
- **Timebound** – related to specific dates when results can be achieved

The target-setting allows for data comparison and enables tracking of any progress towards meeting goals and achieving results.

As a next step, one or more indicators are identified for each one of the expected impacts; indicators that reflect and can quantify the respective impact. A preliminary list of indicators, including targets and units of measurements is presented at the following Table 14. It is noted that the indicators presented in this framework are not considered as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) since they are not always *key* or having a significant effect on the expected impacts (Parmenter, 2015). We will have to collect the current values of these indicators during the project. Data availability will be confirmed at a later stage. Presumably the majority of data already exists, if not we need to make sure indicators suggested are realistic to measure. The list of indicators will be finalised following the feedback from pilots.

Table 14: Sustainable technology evaluation framework

	Expected Impact Area	Target	Indicators	Unit
Economic	Navigability of inland waterways	50% capacity during extreme weather	E1-Capacity levels during extreme weather events E2-Early warning systems for extreme weather	E1- avg % E2- % extreme weather incidents detected / month
	Land/sea/infrastructure resilience	80% capacity level during disruptions	E3-Capacity levels during disruptions E4-Real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring	E3- avg % E4- % of network covered
	Visibility of shipments & Logistics optimisation	TBD	E5-Tracked vs total shipments E6-Operational efficiency E7-Status updates	E5- % /month E6- tonnes/km E7- updates/hour
	Reliability of shipments	80% of cases being on-time	E8-Actual vs planned shipments E9-Delays/Waiting times	E8- % of on-time shipments E9- actual-estimated time of arrival as absolute value per shipment
	Physical Internet and Synchronisation of services	TRL 7	E10-Technical readiness level of technologies E11-Resource availability / Asset management	E10- TRL E11- % of assets digitalised/connected
	Economic efficiency	TBD	E12-Operational cost of a fixed route E13-Overall corridor transit time	E12- euro/cargo unit/km E13- minutes/km
Environmental	Share of inland water transport in the modal split	20% increase of share on IWT	ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT	ENV1- % of total freight
	Recycled materials	30% increase of recycled materials	ENV2-Recycled materials ENV3-Evaluation of material composition applied by IWT infrastructure	ENV2- % ENV3- TBD
	Emissions	TBD	ENV4-NOX ENV5-PM ENV6-GHG as CO2e	ENV4- g/kWh or %m/m ENV5- µg/m3 ENV6- tonnes of CO2e / tkm
	Energy efficiency	TBD	ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre	ENV7- toe /tkm
	Soil/water pollution	TBD	TBD	
Social	Collaboration among stakeholders / Governance models	TBD	S1-Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines	S1- Number of models/solutions

	Safety	TBD	S2-Accidents along the transport network S3-Time to react	S2- Incidents/month S3- response time/return time
	Intermodal / multimodal transportation	TBD	S4-Availability of multimodal transport information	S4- Information publicly available (Likert scale)
	Perception of inland navigation	TBD	S5-Social acceptance survey results	S5- Likert scale

The final list of indicators may be different for each river pilot and will be determined once the availability of data is reported by the pilot sites. For this purpose, the list of indicators will be shared with the leaders of each pilot, to report the availability of data and/or provide alternative indicators for which data is already collected. At least one indicator should be measured for each one of the expected impact areas.

Any indicators developed within the scope of Task 1.4 on Key Innovative Technology Assessment may feed in the framework and vice versa. Other indicators that relate to upcoming WPs and tasks of CRISTAL are: indicators E12 and S1 which receive information from WP4, indicator S5 which will be the content of D9.3 in WP9 as well as E10 as one of the outcomes of Task 10.1 in WP10. Further details on the independencies among WPs and the indicators of the evaluation framework can be found at Table 15 at the end of this chapter.

Step 3 & Step 4: Baseline and TO-BE scenarios

The purpose of Step 3 and Step 4 of the evaluation framework is to collect data and quantify the indicators selected for two time periods; once at a time period before the pilot takes place (baseline scenario) and once after the implementation of the pilot activities (TO-BE scenario).

Step 5: Evaluation outcomes

In order to determine the final outcome of the CRISTAL technologies, different evaluation framework methods can be performed, adopting each time the most appropriate methodological tool as described below. Taking into account the purpose of this evaluation framework, the following six methods are suggested: a) Technical & Operational analysis, b) Financial analysis, c) Vulnerability analysis, and d) Impact analysis. It is noted that Steps 1-4 of the evaluation framework are only relevant and necessary to be completed for the Impact analysis method.

Technical & Operational analysis

The technology validation of the pilots will be performed within Task 10.1 of WP10 which aims to assess the technologies developed. The operational performance of the pilots will be assessed within Task 10.3. In order to evaluate the quality of the technologies, the ISO/ IEC 25010 is recommended to measure different components in relation to their operational feasibility.

Financial analysis

The financial analysis of the developed technologies and CRISTAL solutions will be the focus of Task 4.3.1 within WP4 which aims to quantify the main cost and benefits of the potential implementation of the

developed technologies and the corridor management system. Task 10.2 of WP10 regarding Business Model Validation will also seek information about costs and revenues of the applied solutions. Task 1.4 of WP1 assesses the available technologies including an economic analysis which can feed into the Economic efficiency indicators (depending if TO-BE scenario can be formulated with the same Baseline indicators).

Vulnerability analysis

A vulnerability analysis, in the context of CRISTAL river pilots, refers to the process of identifying, evaluating and prioritising vulnerabilities of transport infrastructure technologies to climate change and other natural or human-caused disruptions (hazards). Such an analysis can be conducted taking into account the probability of occurrence, the magnitude and the potential impact on people, property, operations and the environment (Islam & Ryan, 2016). The vulnerability analysis methodology developed by Islam & Ryan (2016), suggests the following six steps which can be adjusted to suit the context of the river pilots:

1. The evaluation leaders of each pilot identify potential hazards to the successful implementation of pilot activities and deployment of technologies;
2. The hazards are added in the Hazard Vulnerability Assessment matrix (Table 15);
3. Create scenarios that relate to each hazard based on different potential threats (climate change related, other natural or human-caused disruptions);
4. Assign probabilities with values ranging from 0 to 3 (0-Zero, 1-Low, 2-Medium, 3-High) for each hazard and scenario combination;
5. Assess each one of the five impact areas on a scale from 1 to 5. Impact areas refer to assets at risk and can be chosen from the following list: people, property including critical infrastructure, supply chain, systems/equipment, information technology, business operations, reputation of or confidence in entity, regulatory and contractual obligations, environment;
6. Calculate the risk which is derived when multiplying the probability of each hazard/scenario combination by the highest impact rating for any of the five areas.

Once the risk rating is calculated for each one of the identified hazard/scenario combinations, mitigation measures can be formulated for the top ones in the list. A vulnerability analysis can be completed for each river pilot separately. Further details on the methodology presented above can be found in the 'Vulnerability Assessment and Impact Analysis' chapter prepared by Islam & Ryan (2016) as well as at FEMA⁷ guidelines and courses.

⁷ https://emilms.fema.gov/is_0559/groups/142.html;
https://www.fema.gov/pdf/plan/prevent/rms/155/e155_unit_iv.pdf

Table 15: Template for recording hazards in vulnerability analysis

Hazard	Scenario	Probability	Impact with Existing Mitigation					Highest Impact Rating	Risk Rating
			People	Property	Operations	Environment	Entity		
Extreme weather	Sensors fail to measure water depth	2	0	1	3	0	1	3	6
		Probability is based on historical data		Assets at risk: can be selected from the list provided			Probability x Highest impact rating		

Source: adapted from Islam & Ryan (2016)

The Vulnerability Analysis presented in this section can be performed within the scope of Task 12.5 Risk Management of WP12.

Impact analysis

The impact analysis of the river pilots aims to assess the overall impact of the technologies and solutions developed and tested in all three river pilots. In order to perform an impact analysis, it is necessary to quantify both the Baseline and the TO-BE scenarios (Steps 3 and 4), that is to gather data for all indicators selected in Step 2 for the two time periods specified. Measurements of both scenarios can feed into the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) tool as illustrated in Figure 2. The AHP tool can determine the importance of each expected impact and corresponding indicators (criteria) towards reaching a specified goal, and derive the final impact of each river pilot (alternatives).

The impact analysis can be performed within the scope of Task 10.4 regarding Sustainability Validation.

Figure 18: AHP tool to evaluate the sustainability of technologies applied in river pilots based on different criteria

An alternative impact assessment method is the development of an index able to present at a glance the sustainability of technologies based on measurement of different indicators. This approach requires the establishment a lower and maximum value (range) for each indicator which can enable the normalisation

of each indicator to a common scale e.g. from 0 to 1. As a next step, the index can be composed and derive a single value representing the sustainability of technologies for each river pilot.

The most appropriate impact analysis method will be selected at a later stage once the content and activities of the river pilots are formulated in further detail.

The different tasks of the GA that are relevant for the development of the indicators presented in this evaluation framework are presented in the following Table 16.

Table 16: Interrelations between WPs and the Evaluation Framework

Work Package	Task	Relevance to Evaluation Framework and indicators
WP1	Task 1.2 Business processes and requirements identification	All KPIs of the project are identified which can feed into the evaluation framework
	Task 1.4 Key Innovative Technology Assessment	Any indicators developed within the scope of this task and PESTEL analysis may feed into the framework and vice versa
WP3	Task 3.3.1 Early detection systems and alerts	Indicator E2 can be informed by the early detection systems and alerts reviewed in this task
WP4	Task 4.3 Development of the business models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •governance framework financial analysis of the developed technologies and CRISTAL solutions (evaluation outcome in Step 5) •quantification of the main costs and benefits of the developed technologies and the corridor management system can assist in defining indicators e.g. E12 •indicator S1 can receive information from WP4
WP 5	Task 5.1 ff Digital Twin	Digital twin will be used in the evaluation framework
	Task 5.2 Data Warehouse and Data Management	5.2 assists with data management and explores data availability, which is useful for the development of indicators
WP9	Task 9.5 Socio-economic research and recommendations	Indicator S5 can be derived from the results of this task and the corresponding Deliverable 9.3
WP10	Task 10.1 Technology validation	Indicator E10 can be informed by this tasks and Technology Validation will be performed as an evaluation outcome (Step 5)
	Task 10.2 Business Model Validation	This task also seeks information about costs and revenues of the applied solutions, similar to Task 4.3
	Task 10.3 Pilot Operational Performance	Operational Performance of the pilots (evaluation outcome in Step 5)
	Task 10.4 Sustainability Validation	This task includes the implementation of the evaluation framework and impact analysis
WP12	Task 12.5 Risk Management	Vulnerability Analysis (evaluation outcome in Step 5) can be performed within the scope of this task

Step 6: Reporting and overall impact

This step concludes the final output of the three river pilots. Results from the different evaluation methods are analysed and different guidelines and recommendations are generated. The six different evaluation methods presented at Step 5, will produce reports in the form of Deliverables. For example, part of the output of the Technical & Operational analysis will be included in Deliverable 6.2. The Vulnerability analysis method will be part of Deliverable 12.4 regarding the risk management plan. Deliverables 7.2, 8.2 and 9.2 will include impact assessments of the river pilots and Deliverable 10.1 will validate the CRISTAL project building upon the evaluation framework provided in this chapter.

5. Conclusions

IWT has not yet managed to grow at the European scale into being a full alternative to other transport modes. Volumes in IWT are still dominated by bulk cargoes. With the broad exception of the river Rhine and Scheldt, the transport of unitised cargo remains a niche product. Inland waterway has the least dense network of all transport modes and is faced with temporary closures of its infrastructure due to too low or too high-water levels.

The pilot sites in CRISTAL in France, Italy and Poland have in common that they are not among the most developed regions for inland waterways. While inland navigation takes place on the Seine and on the Moselle in France, this mode of transport is hardly developed on the almost unregulated rivers Po in Italy and Vistula in Poland.

The importance of transport infrastructure availability and accessibility is undisputed for road and rail transport with their links and nodes (e.g. terminals or ports). The link infrastructure of inland waterways however falls sometimes a little short in consideration about possible closures. A river is not a given infrastructure that regulates itself. A smarter way to maintain and to keep the infrastructure more available is the rationale for the technology developments undertaken in CRISTAL. Since closures will remain unavoidable to some extent, an enhanced process to be prepared well in advance to substitute IWT by other means of transport is the rationale of the s

The CRISTAL project's ambition is to increase the availability and thus the attractiveness of the inland waterway transport mode. The rationale for this project is the ambition to shift the modal split in the regions under consideration by at least 20% in favour of inland navigation. This can be achieved by the chosen technologies and measures i.e. a better data acquisition for the infrastructure operators but also for the users of the transport infrastructure, a better plannability regarding extreme weather events and other disturbances as well as a better monitoring of the status of the existing quay facilities and bank reinforcements.

Technologies developed and applied must take heterogeneous conditions in the three pilot sites into account. In order that the infrastructure authorities benefit from the technologies and governance processes developed in the project, the dimensions and the scaling must be adapted.

The expectations and the application of the technologies to be developed in CRISTAL will differ in the pilot sites. This is e.g. reasoned by the infrastructure, which is in place along the waterway links. The inspection device only makes sense where concrete walls exist. Different waterflow velocities favour or impede the use of the smart buoys.

All infrastructure authorities welcome the developments in CRISTAL, since they expect an improvement of day-to-day management of their infrastructure and an overall better accessibility through a better resource allocation. Even if the infrastructure authorities are not responsible for the quality of transport and logistic services offered by third parties using their infrastructure, they generally welcome support making IWT more competitive and more accessible.

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VNF 2022 Transport statistics

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Water Law, Dz.U. (2021) item 2233 Article 395 Announcement by the Speaker of the Sejm of the Republic of Poland of 14 October 2021 on the announcement of the consolidated text of the Act - Water Law, Dz.U. 2021 item 2233.

Wody Polskie2022 - Tasks. Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie, <https://wody.gov.pl/o-wodach-polskich/zadania-wod-polskich> [accessed 10.11.2022].

Zukunftsinstitut GmbH 2020 „Megatrends“, <https://www.zukunftsinstitut.de/dossier/megatrends/>

7. Appendices

Annex I – Questionnaire

Basic Information data

Name - Contact person

Name of company

Address of company

Designation (role in inland Waterway transport)

Date of interview

Description of responsibility

Please define the segment of inland waterway(s) you are responsible for incl. administrative responsibilities and boundaries. (for example issues like infrastructure surveillance, traffic control, lock operation, freight handling, tourism, or else).

What tasks must you cover as the responsible institution? (please tick boxes)

- Regulate water levels
- Guarantee drinking water supply
- Guarantee navigability for recreational navigation
- Guarantee navigability for commercial shipping cargo ships
- Management of infrastructure
- Management of suprastructure
- Supply power plants and/or industry with cooling water
- Ensuring accessibility to the infrastructure
- Ensuring the reliability of the infrastructure at a given level of service
- Other (Please provide details)

Which actors are involved in the current inland waterway transport operations as regards the infrastructure of the river or canal?

Please choose from (multiple answers possible):

- IWT infrastructure operator
- Barge operators
- Freight forwarders
- Shippers (cargo owners)
- Terminal operators
- Tech providers
- Other actors (?)

Navigability / Accessibility / Reliability

What is the water class of the inland waterway in question? Please add map or else if segments differ.

I

II

III

IV

Va

Vb

Vla

Vlb

Vlc

Which river information systems RIS are implemented if any? Please specify

Are there currently any functional operational digital platforms in the segment of inland waterway(s) you are responsible for? If yes, which are the digital services offered (please list them) and who is the manager of this/these platform(s)?

Are other IT systems implemented to assist in the operation of the inland waterway? E.g., are there any sensors collecting which feeds any databases and/or IT systems? Are static or dynamic data (and KPIs) already in use (info re. acquisition system, dedicated server where data are stored)

Associated goals	Sensors	Data Acquisition system (e.g. data format, analogue /digital; data sampling frequency; data acquisition format); gateway; monitoring systems	Data Processing	Representation of information for end-users (e.g. indicators summarizing data that could inform decision making process) (e.g. pdf reports; dashboard; GIS webservices; mobile apps, RIS)
Navigability				
Corridor management				
Any other				

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To what extent has the navigability of the inland waterway considered here been restricted in 2022 or/ and in the years before? Please describe the restrictions and indicate the number of weeks per year in which this restriction existed. Please do this for the last years as suitable.

	Restriction in days per year	Description of restriction (fully, partly – if partly please elaborate)	Reason(s) for restriction (see hereunder)
2022			
2021			
2020			
2019			
2018			
2017			
2016			
2015			
2014			

2013			

Possible reasons may include

- Low water due to too little precipitation
- High water due to too much precipitation or snowmelt
- Debris in water after bad weather
- Damaged infrastructure due to extreme weather or decay
- Shipping accidents
- Defective locks
- Strike of workers
- Other (Please elaborate)

Is the accessibility (the ability of users to use the infrastructure) in any way restricted? Is there an agreed service level of accessibility (in terms of physical and operational accessibility)? Please elaborate

In your opinion, do transport operators/ the users have sufficient resources in terms of the accessibility of alternative means of transportation in times of closure of the IWW segment?

Are there currently any established interfaces (e.g. IWW port with rail connection) with other modes of transport (road, rail) in the segment of inland waterway(s) you are responsible for? If yes, please list them

Are reliability levels of services agreed on by any legal binding terms or between stakeholders?

Do you regard climate change as a main driver of future accessibility / reliability / navigability issues? Is it already the case or is that an expectation?

Capacity

Theoretical capacity of the waterway segment regarded here in number of vessels (per water class) and in maximum tonnage per year

Capacity utilisation degree in % of full capacity based on your qualified estimation per season (meteorological spring, summer, fall, winter) or if not available on general average per year.

Spring

Summer

Fall

Winter

Preservation and maintenance of the infrastructure

Which methodology like structural health monitoring (SHM) sensors; or in-situ/laboratory tests do you use to record and detect damage and survey the infrastructure? Is there any preventive or predictive maintenance regime?

	Sensors	Data Acquisition system (e.g. data format, analogue /digital; data sampling frequency; data acquisition format); gateway; monitoring systems	Data Processing	Representation of information for end-users (e.g. indicators summarizing data that could inform decision making process) (e.g. pdf reports; dashboard; GIS webservices; mobile apps)
Preventive or predictive Maintenance				

Do you have structural drawings and/or data about constructive and geometrical characteristics of the infrastructures that you manage? Any structured forms procedure for periodically assessing the state of maintenance? Anything like a digitised 3D model or BIM (Building Information Modelling)?

Do transport operators/ users of your inland waterway have any special requirements that have changed recently and have required you to adapt the infrastructure? Examples would be changed vessel sizes, different

drafts, autonomous navigation, increased share of recreational navigation, other. Please elaborate

Do you regard climate change as a main driver of future infrastructure maintenance demand? Is it already the case or is that an expectation?

Expectations and user requirements regarding new technologies deployed in CRISTAL

Would you need CRISTAL sensors to monitor navigability or what already in place is sufficient? What are your functional expectations regarding the buoys and sensors to measure water levels and other properties of the water? Do you know of any comparable technological solutions?

Would you need CRISTAL sensors for the SHM of your engineered infrastructures or what already in place is sufficient?

Would you need a data acquisition system for CRISTAL sensors or any other sensors that you might already use?

Would you like to have a dashboard and / or a mobile app for representing key performance indicators related to the tasks that you have to undertake? Please tick boxes

Associated goals	Dashboards	Mobile Apps	Digital Twin
Navigability			

Environmental Monitoring/Emergency management			
Syncro-modality			
Capacity Monitoring			
SHM and preventive maintenance planning			
other			

Which technologies are already in use to exchange the data? By which standards?

If the data is not being collected, how is it possible for you to collect this data?

What are your top 3 functional requirements regarding the digital twin? E.g. data Integration from multiple sources, historical data management, integration of external systems

What are your top 3 non-functional requirements regarding the digital twin? E.g. look and feel, security, performance, usability

What are your functional expectations regarding the concrete walls inspection device to measure the status of hydraulic infrastructure?

Would you as the infrastructure operator benefit in any sense from a synchro-modal corridor management system that would be available to users like shippers or forwarders? E.g., by being able to offer a more reliable transport solution in conjunction with such a tool?

To what extent would data about the navigability (intelligent buoys for controlled waterways or Fiber Optic sensors for free-flowing waterways) and preventive maintenance sensors (I.e. inspection radar) be processed and synthetised into meaningful KPIs that can enrich actual data? Do you have any proposal for KPIs?

Without any additional data and tools, how is planning carried out today in terms of expected extreme weather events and the resulting low or high water levels? How do you do it? Please elaborate!

Are there any severe shortcomings by the recent processes? What good experiences did you have if any?

To what extent would you need or are you already using detailed forecasts of precipitation probabilities in your region? Do you evaluate this data manually or does this data find its input into any planning models?

Is an integration with existing River Information Systems RIS desirable or even mandatory?

Which business case (scenario) do you find particularly interesting to test in advance in a digital twin? Please give a short description.

Do you see a digital twin as a good tool to test and plan for the operation of your facilities? What advantages do you hope to gain from using it?

Should such a digital twin also include questions about infrastructure maintenance and its status, or are you more interested in traffic operations that are as trouble-free as possible?

Annex 2: List of actors in the IWT market

If all actors that belong to the transport chain in which IWT is deployed are also regarded as stakeholders is a matter of definition.

The following actors can be defined in the IWT market as intermediate users or end users.

Actor	Description	Proposed to be regarded as a stakeholder within the CRISTAL project
Barge operator	A company that provides barge capacity and barge transport.	X
Consignee	The ultimate receiver of the shipper consignment	X
Consignor	The ultimate sender of a shipment.	X
Forwarder	A company that is specialised in carrying out the forwarding function on behalf of a shipper. The company can either only carry out that forwarding function or can additionally offer further logistical services and/or owns rolling road stock.	X
Intermodal operator	A company that offers the organisation of either a door-to-door or a terminal-to terminal transportation chain by using the means of intermodal transport. Intermodal operators are those actors that combine and refine the crude rail haulage capacity of individual railways, adding to it specific support services and making it into a saleable product. Their status may be railway, or railway-owned (as ICF), or largely private as the UIRR companies.	X
Logistic service provider	A company that offers logistic services like warehousing, storage, stuffing and stripping, etc., but in any way other services than just transport and forwarding.	X
Operator	Represented in the transport chain as forwarder, intermodal operator, agent or terminal operator having each of their function either to plan and/or to control each transport stage and/or load unit handling in the terminals.	X

D1.1 Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements

Actor	Description	Proposed to be regarded as a stakeholder within the CRISTAL project
Policy actor	Representative of a group of interests within a country community, a country or a region, influencing decisions of transport actors concerning the choice of the means of transport by policy frameworks such as fiscal and order policy measures.	
Railways	A company operating and/or owning rolling railway stock providing rail traction services.	X
Road haulier	A company operating and /or owning trucks and carrying out road transport functions concentrating on the physical movements of goods.	X
Shipper	The owner of the cargo when it is dispatched. It can be either a consignee or a consignor. A representative of the consumer demand side.	X
Shipping line/ coastal/ oversea shipping line	A company operating and /or owning vessels for sea transport.	X
Stevedoring company	A company responsible for the storage of goods at terminals.	
Terminal operator	A party, a company or a department of a company planning and maintaining the use of means of transport, handling equipment at a transshipment point. Provision of transshipment services to parties like intermodal operators and road hauliers.	X
Transport operator	A party, a company or a department of a company, planning and maintaining the use of means of transport or equipment of a transport stage.	X
Transport organiser	A party, a company or a department organising and planning a part of a transport chain.	X

Table 17: End users in the IWT transport market

The interrelation between the actors can be illustrated in the following manner:

Figure 19: Actors in the intermodal chain; Source: Ceulemans (2021)

Figure 20: Actors in sea and inland ports; Source: Van der Horst (2016)

Both figures illustrate well the number of actors and their possible interrelation within the IWT transport chain. These interrelations and processes will be further analysed in Deliverable 1.2.

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